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THE EVOLUTION OF THE MULTICULTURAL APPROACH TO FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN DOMESTIC EDUCATION AT THE END OF THE 20TH – BEGINNING OF THE 21ST CENTURIES

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Abstract. At the end of the 20th century, against the background of rapidly expanding political, economic and socio-cultural cooperation between Russia and Western countries, interest in learning foreign languages increased. The country needed specialists who could quickly become involved in international cooperation in all fields of activity. However, the need to prepare for intercultural communication revealed the insufficiency of existing approaches to teaching a foreign language, and the grammatical and translation orientation of the educational process required a significant transformation in order to ensure the formation of students' communication skills and knowledge about the culture of the country of the studied language. Rethinking the goal-oriented priorities of the discipline "Foreign Language" led to the development of new approaches to teaching a foreign language, an important of which was the multicultural approach. The paper characterizes the economic and socio-cultural factors of the emergence of a multicultural approach to teaching foreign languages, analyzes state documents that have consolidated the need to expand the cultural component of the process of learning a foreign language, gives a theoretical description of multicultural education, highlights its components, principles, interpretations of the multicultural approach, analyzes its role in obtaining cultural knowledge about the country of the studied language, necessary for productive international cooperation, implementation technologies are shown. The main provisions of the concept of multicultural approach by V.I. Mathis, as well as the concept of linguistic multicultural education developed by P.V. Sysoev, are studied. Attention is drawn to the functioning of various educational organizations that contribute to the development of multicultural education. The methods of teaching are called, the implementation of which will contribute to the formation of not only language skills, but, no less importantly, information about the culture of the country of the studied language on the indispensable basis of knowledge about the native culture. The authors conclude that the implementation of a multicultural approach to teaching foreign languages will contribute to the development of multicultural thinking, humanity, tolerance, respect for other cultures, which will become the basis for successful interaction in a global society.

Keywords: approach, multicultural education, multicultural approach

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ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ ПОЛИКУЛЬТУРНОГО ПОДХОДА К ОБУЧЕНИЮ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ В ОТЕЧЕСТВЕННОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ В КОНЦЕ XX – НАЧАЛЕ XXI ВВ.

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Аннотация. В конце XX столетия на фоне стремительно расширяющегося политического, экономического и социокультурного сотрудничества России с западными странами усиливается интерес к изучению иностранных языков. Стране требовались специалисты, которые могли быстро включаться в международное взаимодействие во всех сферах деятельности. Однако необходимость подготовки к межкультурному общению выявила недостаточность существующих подходов к обучению иностранному языку, а грамматико-переводческая направленность учебного процесса требовала существенной трансформации, чтобы обеспечить формирование у обучающихся коммуникативных навыков и получение знаний о культуре страны изучаемого языка. Переосмысление целевых приоритетов дисциплины «Иностранный язык» повлекло разработку новых подходов к обучению иностранному языку, важным из которых стал поликультурный подход. В работе характеризуются экономические и социокультурные факторы возникновения поликультурного подхода к обучению иностранным языкам, анализируются государственные документы, которые закрепили необходимость расширения культурологического компонента процесса изучения иностранного языка, дана теоретическая характеристика поликультурного образования, выделяются его компоненты, принципы, даются трактовки поликультурного подхода, анализируется его роль в получении культурологических знаний о стране изучаемого языка, необходимых для продуктивного международного взаимодействия, показаны технологии реализации. Изучаются основные положения концепции поликультурного подхода В.И. Матиса, а также концепции языкового поликультурного образования, разработанной П.В. Сысоевым. Обращается внимание на функционирование различных образовательных организаций, способствующих развитию поликультурного образования. Называются методы обучения, реализация которых будет способствовать формированию не только языковых навыков, но что не менее важно – сведений о культуре страны изучаемого языка на неперменной основе знаний о родной культуре. Авторы приходят к выводу, что реализация поликультурного подхода к обучению иностранным языкам будет способствовать развитию поликультурного мышления, гуманности, толерантности, уважения к другим культурам, что станет основой успешного взаимодействия в глобальном обществе.

Ключевые слова: подход, поликультурное обучение, поликультурный подход

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Introduction

With the world becoming more interconnected, the constant exchange between nations and their citizens has become a daily norm. This shift highlights the importance of equipping students to recognize, interpret, and appreciate the wide range of languages and cultures they will encounter. Without this preparation, effective communication across different cultures becomes challenging.

As the 20th century transitioned into the 21st, Russia's national strategy concentrated on bolstering political, economic, and socio-cultural ties with Western nations. The swift expansion of economic collaboration, along with Russia's assimilation into the global economic landscape to secure enduring economic prosperity, the establishment of joint business ventures, the inflow of foreign investment, the escalation of trade between involved parties, and the modernization of domestic industry, collectively created a pressing demand for professionals proficient in foreign languages.

The 1990s to early 2000s were marked by an increase in cultural cooperation between our country and Western nations, along with the signing of various agreements in culture, science, and education. Foreign cultural policy is aimed at popularization and dissemination of Russian culture and the Russian language in the world.

However, the rapidly increasing interaction required not only knowledge of a foreign language, but, no less importantly, the culture of the country, taking into account the cultural and historical characteristics of all parties in order to build conflict-free relations.

This research paper aims to chart the development of a multicultural approach to foreign language education in Russia from the late 20th to the early 21st century. During this period, significant shifts occurred in foreign language teaching methods across all educational levels. There was a reassessment of objectives and a quest for approaches that could transition the traditional grammar and translation-focused system into a practical, communication-centric model. This new model emphasized not only linguistic proficiency but also cultural understanding related to the language being studied. One notable approach that emerged was the multicultural method, which became instrumental in fostering a deeper comprehension of

the target language's culture, including its unique mindset, lifestyle, traditions, and customs.

In this paper, the main attention will be focused on the evolution of a multicultural approach to teaching foreign languages in Russia during the late XX — early XXI century. We will analyze existing scientific papers published during this period in order to identify key trends and changes in approaches to teaching foreign languages. The factors contributing to the development of a multicultural approach will be identified, an analysis of official state documents will be carried out to understand the stages of development of multicultural approach. In summary, this study will show how the implementation of a multicultural approach affected students' language skills and their preparedness for intercultural communication. Based on the results obtained, we will develop recommendations for incorporating a multicultural approach into contemporary foreign language teaching practices.

Methodology

We used general scientific methods of cognition, with particular emphasis on the systematic analysis of scientific literature regarding the teaching of foreign languages in this scientific work, also theory and practice of a multicultural approach to teaching foreign languages. The educational reform in Russia in the 90s of the XXth century marked the priority of the personality-oriented paradigm of education and upbringing. This fact has prompted teachers to develop new cultural and personal approaches. Such culturological approaches are beginning to gain the greatest popularity: linguistic and cultural (A.G. Krupko, G.D. Tomakhin, N.A. Salanovich), socio-cultural (V.V. Safonova, P.V. Sysoev), regional (A.D. Reichstein), intercultural (G.A. Maslikova) and their derivatives.

O.V. Gukalenko, N.V. Kuzmina, I.Y. Makurina, L.L. Suprunova, P.V. Sysoev were engaged in the study of the multicultural approach during this period in our country, who put forward the task of forming a personality through comprehension of cultural information. In this context, the multicultural approach in teaching foreign languages is aimed at studying various cultural facts about the country of the studied language, which should contribute to a deeper understanding of the versatility of the cultural context in which the language functions. In the future, this should aid in establishing conditions that promote harmonious

interaction among representatives of various nationalities and prevent misunderstandings that occur during the communication.

In examining the multicultural approach to foreign language education, several methods were employed, including periodization, analysis, conceptualization, comparison, generalization, and data interpretation. At the academic level, the historical and genetic method was utilized to trace the origin and evolution of the multicultural approach, providing insights into its developmental trajectory. Additionally, the historical and chronological method was applied to determine the sequence of changes and identify trends in the progression of this approach.

Discussion

The origin of the first prerequisites for the formulation of multicultural issues in foreign language education began in the 80s of the twentieth century. The need for knowledge of foreign languages has led to changes in the educational policy in our country. As stipulated by Federal laws, regulations, decrees, and orders, along with the Concept of Modernization of Russian Education and Federal State standards, as well as other regulatory documents, there has been a shift in the conceptual foundations and trajectories shaping the policy landscape for foreign language education.

According to «the Decree of the President of the RSFSR of July 11, 1991 No. 1 "On priority measures for the development of education in the RSFSR (with amendments and additions)"» [17], paragraph 4 states "to send annually abroad for training, internships, advanced training at least 10 thousand students, graduate students, teachers and scientific and pedagogical workers" [17]. It becomes clear that the purpose of these trips is training, internships and advanced training, but participants will immerse themselves in a different linguistic and cultural environment, which required both knowledge of the language and knowledge of the culture.

The 1992 Law on Education also states that the content of education must ensure (among others) the "integration of the individual into national and world culture" [19]. Mutual understanding and cooperation between peoples are impossible without foreign languages, so the educational process should increasingly rely on cultural approaches to learning.

Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 418 dated April 25, 1995 "On the Concept of State Policy to support partnership between educational institutions of the Russian Federation and foreign educational institutions established with the assistance of the USSR" [11], Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation dated May 23, 1995. No. 498 "On the development of the system of higher and secondary vocational education in the Russian Federation" [10] and the Federal Law "On Higher and Postgraduate Vocational Education" [4] of 1996 consolidated the right and opportunity to participate in international cooperation through exchange programs, joint research and events, which also required proficiency in at least one foreign language.

Federal Law No. 51 of April 10, 2000 "On approval of the Federal Program for the Development of Education" [13] required "to improve mechanisms for ensuring international exchanges, participation of students and specialists of the education system in international conferences, symposiums, seminars, fairs of educational services, student and school Olympiads, and other international events" [13]. As societies become more open and integrated into the global sphere, they are forging stronger political, economic, and cultural bonds between nations. This increased interconnectivity has led to a growing demand for foreign language skills. Consequently, more people are seeking to learn new languages to participate effectively in this interconnected world.

The topic of development and expansion of international cooperation was raised in governmental documents for a reason. Without knowledge of a foreign language, participation in international programs and exchanges seemed difficult. An important aspect was the formation of a holistic worldview and the development of a culture of interethnic relations.

On the basis of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, the Laws "On Education" [19], "On Higher Postgraduate professional Education" [4], "On the Languages of the Peoples of the Russian Federation", and the National Doctrine of Education in the Russian Federation (for the period up to 2025) [12], the Concept of Development multicultural education [7] in the Russian Federation was formed, the general provisions of which indicated, that the modernization of

Russian education is possible only with an integrated innovative system of multicultural education. According to the Concept, multicultural education will take into account "state interests, national and ethno-cultural characteristics of the population, the conditions of intercultural dialogue and the tasks of designing inter-ethnic and interfaith harmony" [7].

The Concept of multicultural education aims to cultivate a creative and well-rounded individual who comprehends their national and civic identity within the context of both Russian and global cultures. Additionally, it seeks to empower individuals to engage responsibly and productively in intellectual, organizational, and industrial pursuits within an open, multicultural, and multilingual world. Furthermore, it underscores the significance of preserving and developing national cultures and languages within Russia, recognizing these as essential for the socialization of youth and the establishment of a strong state [7].

The concept of multicultural education development in the Russian Federation asserts that the modernization of education can occur only through a comprehensive innovative system that considers state interests, national and ethnocultural characteristics, intercultural dialogue, and interethnic harmony. One of the key objectives is to cultivate well-rounded people with a strong sense of self-awareness. Another aim is to equip them with the skills necessary to contribute effectively in a diverse, multicultural landscape. Additionally, there is a focus on safeguarding and advancing national cultures and languages to facilitate youth integration into society. This ultimately reinforces the strength and unity of the state.

So, the development of a multicultural approach to teaching foreign languages in our country was largely influenced by the expansion of international cooperation, which was determined by foreign state policy and documented in state documents. Being one of the cultural approaches, the multicultural approach began its development with state requirements for international cooperation, integration into world culture, support for partnerships between educational and scientific institutions, and modernization of the educational process.

At the end of the XX century, multicultural Russia gains special significance, highlighting the importance of forming multicultural competence. In this

regard, the active development of a multicultural approach begins.

It should be noted that multicultural education recognizes the presence of many cultures of equal value, and their interaction has a beneficial effect on society as a whole. Multicultural education is aimed at ensuring a harmonious introduction of the individual to foreign and native culture. It turns out that a person in communication with representatives of other cultures seeks to understand their special system of values and views.

In his research, V.I. Mathis examined the education system of the late 1990s and identified the following shortcomings: excessive emphasis on objective learning, neglect of students' self-development, rigid standardization, formalism, authoritarian leadership style, teaching and a disdainful attitude towards education as a secondary activity in relation to learning. To rethink the attitude to education and training, V.I. Mathis proposed the concept of a multicultural approach. The multicultural approach is "a set of ideas and principles of pedagogical activity that determine the purpose, content, positions and ways of interaction between educators and students in the pedagogical process" [9].

According to the author, the development of a multicultural approach began with an analysis of educational problems in changing socio-economic conditions, what new tasks have emerged in the field of education. The introduction of a multicultural approach to education and upbringing creates a multicultural humanistic democratic educational environment. The author notes that the multicultural approach is "the integration of people into a global integrity, into a multicultural community – the main trend of our time" [9]. In the perspective offered, the upcoming multicultural society is envisioned as a cohesive social structure that brings together individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. The longevity of this society is ensured by weaving cultural components into its institutions. It is also maintained by offering a diverse array of social roles for individuals to engage in. Furthermore, the society thrives by fostering and supporting individuals based on their distinctive cultural characteristics. This approach creates an inclusive environment that values and leverages cultural diversity.

In 2004, P.V. Sysoev proposed the concept of linguistic multicultural education. He said that the discipline "Foreign language" is an important tool for the

secondary socialization of the student's personality, which models its socio-cultural space (general ideas about the world are formed). In his opinion, linguistic multicultural education means that the curricula of disciplines include information about the culture of the country of the studied language and the native culture of students. It is also important to take into account how the relationship between language and culture is implemented.

The author emphasizes the importance of including data on the diversity of cultures existing in the native country, region or locality in the process of multicultural education. This approach helps students recognize cultural diversity as a standard feature of modern multicultural societies. It encourages them to see this diversity as an opportunity for cultures to coexist and learn from one another. This understanding is cultivated both within their own country and in the nations whose languages they are studying. By doing so, students become more attuned to the interconnected nature of different cultures in today's world. The range of subjects included in the curricula is essential for providing students with the chance to gain a profound comprehension of their identity within the framework of various cultures, which subsequently fosters their cultural self-determination. "The main common goal of linguistic multicultural education is to prepare students for active and full-fledged cooperation in the modern multicultural world by means of the studied language" [15].

N.V. Bogovik also states that the conclusion of the twentieth century marked the onset of the development of the theoretical foundations for contemporary multicultural education through foreign language studies. The study emphasizes that knowledge of a foreign language cannot be limited by knowledge of vocabulary, grammar and phonetics. "Being a broader concept, it represents mastering the culture of one's own people, as an indispensable condition for integration into other cultures, and a foreign-language communicative culture" [1]. Modern society needs high-quality foreign-language multicultural education, which will form multicultural thinking, social stability, morality, humanity and practical skills for students to live in an ever-changing world.

As N.V. Bogovik's research shows, in 2009 innovative educational institutions and international educational centers began to appear on the territory of

our country, in such cities as Barnaul, Gorno-Altaysk, Krasnoyarsk, Novosibirsk and Tomsk. Public organizations such as the Altai Regional Public Youth Organization "Unit", the Altai Youth Foundation, the German Youth Association "Jugendring" are being created, which contribute to the development of multicultural education and the introduction of a multicultural approach to teaching foreign languages, using various competitions, festivals, lectures, master classes dedicated to various cultures and languages, including the exchange of experience with representatives of other cultures and countries.

V.M. Eremina states that multicultural education has the potential to serve as an effective mechanism for the creation of a humane and democratic society. "Foreign language teachers are tasked with ensuring a dialogue of a new type of culture with previous cultures and a dialogue of national cultures in a global context" [2]. The author outlines several key components in the realm of multicultural education. These include fostering socio-cultural identification, which involves recognizing and embracing one's own cultural identity while also becoming familiar with other cultures. Additionally, it encompasses understanding the world's diversity, acknowledging the variety of natural, cultural, social, and economic phenomena. The approach also advocates for nurturing a positive attitude towards different cultures, aiming to create a harmonious society where individuals can interact regardless of cultural differences. Furthermore, it emphasizes developing skills that promote peaceful coexistence among people from diverse cultural backgrounds and traditions [2].

In the study, the author also suggests using the following technologies of multicultural education, such as: technologies of personality-oriented education, interactive technologies and technologies for learning about different cultures and cultural phenomena. Thus, we understand that the key features of a multicultural approach to teaching foreign languages are cooperation between students.

A vital component is understanding the interplay between the cultural aspects of different groups. This includes examining how the culture of a specific group relates to that of other groups, particularly those of the native country and the country whose language is being studied. It is not just about learning the material of

a single culture in isolation. Selecting educational materials that provide insights into both nations' cultures is crucial. This enables students to authentically compare and contrast cultural elements. Through this process, they can discern both the commonalities and distinctions in various cultural aspects. By focusing on the comparison of the cultural contexts of the two countries, students can achieve a more profound understanding of these environments. This comparative approach highlights the mutual influences between cultures. The educational materials employed in foreign language instruction can establish an atmosphere conducive to multicultural linguistic education. This not only enhances the overall learning experience but also contributes to the development of students' intercultural competence. Through this method, students become better equipped to navigate and appreciate diverse cultural landscapes. Ultimately, it fosters a more enriching and comprehensive educational journey.

L.L. Suprunova emphasizes that one of the key directions for modernizing education in a post-industrial society is preparing young people for integration and active participation amid the cultural diversity present in society. She notes that in modern educational institutions, students from various ethnic, racial and religious groups, as well as belonging to various social strata. They speak different languages and are guided by a variety of cultural values and norms of behavior [14].

In the context of this cultural diversity, educators encounter a significant professional challenge: should they consider students' cultural diversity and socio-cultural traits in the educational process, or should they maintain a neutral stance, disregarding these elements? The task of choosing an approach to the educational process is becoming especially relevant and requires a comprehensive analysis.

Clearly, adopting a multicultural approach is essential. It fosters respect for cultural diversity. Additionally, it equips young people with the necessary skills to thrive in a multicultural society, preparing them for a fulfilling life in a diverse world.

E.A. Isaev writes that this approach "contributes to the assimilation by students of the phenomena of cultural diversity, perceived as a social norm and personal value" [6]. As a result of this process, a personality is formed as a result of creative intercultural interaction.

In his research, E.A. Isaev developed a passport of a multicultural approach, in which he points out that a multicultural approach contributes to the creation of a multicultural environment, which, by learning and introducing students to another culture, fosters "professionalism in its cultural identification" [6]. The author notes that the knowledge of multiculturalism will help to develop language skills and ensure the self-realization of a person in a multicultural world. From the research, we understand that the multicultural approach represents the development of a linguistic personality, multicultural self-organization and cultural self-determination.

A.T. Telegina and E.V. Ryzhova believe that multiculturalism of education is a reflection of the specific features of different cultures, i.e. a reflection of their dialogue and interaction in a historical and modern context. They include the tasks of multicultural education:

- 1) familiarization with the culture of one's own people;
- 2) formation of ideas about the diversity of cultures in general;
- 3) education of respect for cultural differences;
- 4) development of ethnic tolerance and humane interethnic communication;
- 5) the ability to interact with representatives of other cultures [16].

Therefore, multiculturalism is the ability to engage in a dialogue and support people of other cultures, enriching one's own culture. Researchers also emphasize the significance of cultivating a multicultural perspective in students during foreign language classes. This involves thoughtfully choosing the topics covered in educational materials. The selection should be based on cultural approaches that integrate various cultural elements. Additionally, the principle of professional orientation should guide this process. By doing so, educators can effectively foster a multicultural mindset in their students. It is proposed to use interactive learning tools, encourage discussions, role-playing games, presentations, projects, as well as active interaction and cooperation between the teacher and the student.

The main idea is that language is a reflection of culture and a mechanism for its transmission from

generation to generation, contributing to the formation of a multicultural personality. Foreign language classes serve as a crossroads of cultures and a practice ground for intercultural communication. Teaching should highlight the unique aspects of a nation's heritage, including its science, art, and traditions, and employ active learning methods like role-playing and cultural exchanges to foster intercultural interaction. Incorporating knowledge from related fields such as literature, geography, and history can deepen understanding of cultural values and shape attitudes towards other nations. It is recommended to analyze the local lore knowledge of students and organize micro-excursions for foreign guests.

In recent years, scientists have been talking about the need to use as many ways as possible to prepare students for intercultural interaction. According to A.N. Kornienko, engaging students through active and productive teaching methods is essential. This includes activities such as discussions and case studies. Additionally, foreign language presentations and creative tasks play a crucial role. These methods aim to analyze socio-cultural issues. Ultimately, they help develop students' communication skills. Practical classes should be brought as close as possible to the real activities of future graduates. After analyzing various studies, the author comes to the conclusion that it is advisable to use a multicultural approach to teaching foreign languages. The distinctive feature of the multicultural approach is that it encourages the integration of knowledge from different fields and its practical application. This approach enhances students' interest in learning languages and cultures, fosters the development of their personalities, promotes the growth of independent cognitive skills, and cultivates responsibility for the outcomes of collaborative work [8].

A comparable viewpoint is shared by O.V. Gukalenko and V.P. Borisenkov, who highlight those swift changes in the contemporary world have resulted in a shift of priorities in both society and education. Their studies indicate that present-day challenges necessitate a reevaluation of the educational paradigm, which, in turn, means there is a need to create a new education model. In this model, particular emphasis should be placed on a humanistic worldview, along

with the principles of justice and culture, which is fundamental for the formation of a sustainable educational process adequate to the requirements of the XXI century. "Multiculturalism is a qualitative characteristic of a personality, which testifies to its ability to live and function successfully in a multicultural environment, respect and accept cultural differences, provided their humanistic content" [5].

Advancing multicultural ideas has the potential to dismantle negative perceptions and attitudes directed towards representatives of other cultures, thereby fostering an environment in which cultures are seen as complementary elements coexisting within a harmonious and interconnected whole. In their scholarly investigations, the authors emphasize a set of core principles that underpin multicultural education, namely cultural conformity, which encourages respect for diverse cultural norms; multiculturalism, which promotes the value of cultural diversity; cultural integrity, which advocates for the preservation and respect of individual cultural identities; accessibility and openness, which ensure that cultural experiences and knowledge are readily available and shared among all; and finally, intercultural dialogue, which facilitates meaningful exchange and understanding between different cultural groups. Each of these principles is aimed at developing universal skills that promote openness to other cultures and promote intercultural cooperation.

D.K. Voronina and A.N. Shamov emphasize the importance of English as a common language of communication (*lingua franca*) in the educational environment. They note that even students who do not study the language as a core subject understand its importance [18]. However, there is a problem: many students do not realize that native speakers can be very different from their usual images of an "English-speaking foreigner". This leads to the need to create a multicultural environment for language learning to help students understand the diversity of people using English. In general, the emphasis is on the importance of taking cultural differences into account in the learning process.

Thus, the introduction of a multicultural approach will help to educate the moral personality of a

future specialist. Such a specialist will be able to realize not only the technical tasks facing him, but also have the ability to comprehend his professional activity in the global cultural space.

Conclusions

In conclusion, it is pertinent to observe that the genesis and subsequent evolution of a multicultural approach to foreign language instruction emerged as a direct response to the pressing need to revolutionize the process of teaching foreign languages. This shift was driven by the necessity to integrate the study of language and culture within a pedagogical framework that reflected the burgeoning international cooperation characteristic of the 1990s. This decade witnessed an unprecedented expansion of global interconnectedness, which demanded a more holistic approach to language education, one that acknowledged and embraced the intrinsic link between language and cultural understanding. The multicultural approach emerged as a response to the challenges and opportunities of our interconnected world. In this context, proficiency in a foreign language is more than just a linguistic skill. It serves as a key to understanding and navigating various cultural environments. By mastering a

new language, individuals gain insights into different cultures. This makes a multicultural approach essential for thriving in today's diverse global landscape. The study of state documents revealed their significant impact on the modernization of foreign language learning, to develop a multicultural approach to the organization of the educational process. The development of a multicultural approach was carried out in the context of intensification of international cooperation, integration into the world of economy, science and culture.

The analysis of the works of scientists and teachers showed that they expressed essentially similar opinions about the importance of a multicultural approach in forming students' awareness of cultural diversity as a necessary condition for the harmonious coexistence of peoples and the development of cultures. Therefore, modern society places demands on high-quality foreign-language multicultural education, which should contribute to the development of multicultural thinking, social stability, morality, humanity, tolerance. The use of a multicultural approach is an important step towards the formation of a personality who is ready and able to solve both personal and professional tasks in today's complex multicultural world.

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